

A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF RESILIENCE TRAINING'S INFLUENCE ON ARMY NATIONAL GUARDSMEN'S RESILIENCE AND PERFORMANCE

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BACKGROUND OF THE PROBLEM

Overarching Concern: Administrative Flags due to APFT and ABCP Failure

- The failure rates for the **Active Duty Army** are 3% for the APFT and 0.75% for ABCP
- The failure rates for the **Army National Guard** are 11.7% for the APFT and 4.4% for ABCP
- The average cost to replace a soldier separated for APFT/ABCP is ~\$180,000.00

Potential Way Forward: Resilience Training

- Resilience Training results in enhanced motivation, initiating behaviors, and self-efficacy
- The Army's Master Resilience Training (MRT) program
- Army National Guards of Ss & Ts conducting Resilience-based Intervention (Wellness Camp)

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Army National Guard has higher rates of APFT Failure and ABCP non-compliance than the Active Duty Army causing increased administrative flags.

2011: The Army Resilience program designed to combat suicidality concerns

Resilience By Product: Enhanced self-efficacy, motivation, and behavior initiation.

Army Doctrine: National Guardsmen get less frequent resilience training than the Active Duty Army.

PURPOSE STATEMENT

- Quantitative, Quasi-Experimental, Ex Post Facto Study
- Examined the effectiveness of Resilience-Intervention for Army National Guardsmen.
- Goal: Statistically significant relationships in the areas of Resilience, APFT performance, ABCP performance, GS, EC, IM, and EA.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS/HYPOTHESES

- **RQ1.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on perceived levels of resilience when compared before and after intervention in traditional National Guard soldiers who fail to meet the Army's physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
 - **H1.** Statistical Significant Relationships will be established. To the differences between pre/post.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS/HYPOTHESES

- **RQ2.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on Army Physical Fitness Testing Scores on record fitness testing when compared to before and after record fitness testing results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
 - **H2.** Statistical Significant Relationships will be established. To the differences between pre/post.
- **RQ3.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on body composition testing outcomes for record body composition screenings when compared to before and after record body composition screening results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
 - **H3.** Statistical Significant Relationships will be established. To the differences between pre/post.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS/HYPOTHESES

RQ4. To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of **goal setting** as a performance enhancement resilience strategy when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

- **H4.** Statistical Significant Relationships will be established. To the differences between pre/post.

RQ5. To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of **emotional control** performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

- **H5.** Statistical Significant Relationships will be established. To the differences between pre/post.

RQ6. To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of **imagery** performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

- **H6.** Statistical Significant Relationships will be established. To the differences between pre/post.

RQ7. To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of **energy activation** performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

- **H7.** Statistical Significant Relationships will be established. To the differences between pre/post.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Adult Learning Theory

- Non-traditional learners (25+)
- Four Principles:
 - Involve in process
 - Leverage past experiences
 - Establish relevance
 - Problem-centered learning
- Five Assumptions:
 - Self-directed/independence, intrinsic motivation, use immediately, applicable to current role, and draw upon experiences

Resilience Theory

- Process-based
- Enhances self-efficacy
- Can be learned
- Enables positive adaptation to adversity

**THE
STUDY**

NG Soldiers taught resilience through the lens of the Adult Learning Theory

Methodology

Research Design

- Quasi-Experimental
- Ex Post Facto
- Quantitative
- Outcome Comparison

Data Analysis

- SPSS Analysis Process:
 - Two-way ANOVAs
 - Bivariate Testing:
 - Independent Sample T-Test (Gender)
 - One-Way ANOVA (Age Bracket)
- G*Power: Effect Size

Data Collection

- Pre-existing data from NG records.
- Hosting NG State's G3 Training Officer approved.
- N=87 NG Soldiers

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ASSUMPTIONS

Data access permission and honest survey results

STATISTICAL ASSUMPTIONS

ANOVA: Homogeneity of variance; normal distribution of population; robust ANOVA; and identical variance

LIMITATIONS

Command-directed/not volunteers; geographic distribution; no command authority

DELIMITATIONS

Memorandum of Intent (MOI) and contact lists

FINDINGS

• RQ1. Perception of resilience:

- ANOVA: Statistically significant relationship between the intervention and the post-intervention BRS scores; difference of perception of resilience value of 1.76 ($SD=4.95$), $F(1,86)=10.99$, $p<0.001$, $PES=0.113$ (Medium Effect Size)
 - No relationship was found based on age brackets: One-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=0.44$, $p=0.72$) or gender group: Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=-1.50$, $p=0.14$)
- **Null hypothesis was rejected.**

• RQ2. Army Physical Fitness Testing Performance:

- ANOVA: Statistically significant relationship between the intervention and the post-intervention APFT scores; difference of APFT performance value of 38.14 ($SD=28.19$), $F(1,86)=159.27$, $p<0.001$, $PES=0.649$ (Large Effect Size)
 - No relationship was found based on age brackets: One-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=1.46$, $p=0.23$) or gender group: Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=-0.69$, $p=0.49$)
- **Null hypothesis was rejected.**

FINDINGS

- **RQ3. Body composition testing outcomes**

- ANOVA: Statistically significant relationship between the intervention and the post-intervention ABCP screening; difference of ABCP screening outcome of -2.46 ($SD=2.20$), $F(1,86)=108.92$, $p<0.001$, $PES=0.559$ (Large Effect Size)
 - No relationship was found based on age brackets: One-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=2.40$, $p=0.07$) or gender group: Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=-0.11$, $p=0.91$).
- **Null hypothesis was rejected.**

- **RQ4. Application of goal setting**

- ANOVA: Statistically significant relationship between the intervention and the post-intervention Goal Setting (GS) application; difference of GS application outcome of 0.72 ($SD=0.91$), $F(1,86)=54.54$, $p<0.001$, $PES=0.388$ (Large Effect Size)
 - No relationship was found based on age brackets: One-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=0.31$, $p=0.82$) or gender group: Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=-0.41$, $p=0.68$).
- **Null hypothesis was rejected.**

FINDINGS

• **RQ5. Application of emotional control**

- ANOVA: Statistically significant relationship between the intervention and the post-intervention Emotional Control (EC) application; difference of EC application outcome of 0.28 ($SD=0.51$), $F(1,86)=27.15$, $p<0.001$, $PES=0.240$ (Medium Effect Size)
 - No relationship was found based on age brackets: One-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=1.58$, $p=0.20$) or gender group: Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=0.63$, $p=0.53$).
- **Null hypothesis was rejected.**

• **RQ6. Application of imagery**

- ANOVA: Statistically significant relationship between the intervention and the post-intervention Imagery (IM) application; difference of IM application outcome of 0.65 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=80.25$, $p<0.001$, $PES=0.483$ (Large Effect Size)
 - No relationship was found based on age brackets: One-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=0.25$, $p=0.86$) or gender group: Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=0.10$, $p=0.55$)
- **Null hypothesis was rejected.**

FINDINGS

- **RQ7. Application of energy activation**

- ANOVA: Statistically significant relationship between the intervention and the post-intervention Energy Activation (EA) application; difference of EA application outcome of 0.53 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=52.77$, $p<0.001$, $PES=0.380$ (Large Effect Size)
 - No relationship was found based on the differences between outcomes due to age brackets: One-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=1.27$, $p=0.29$) or gender group: Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=0.83$, $p=0.29$).
- **Null hypothesis was rejected.**

RECOMMENDATIONS

STUDY RESULTS

- Re-examine doctrinal guidance
- Prioritization of funds
- Prioritize attendance

FUTURE RESEARCH

- Long term follow-up (six-month and one-year)
- Address Learner Generations (Generation X, Millennials, and Generation Z)

External Validity

- Conduct RCT (intervention and control groups)
- Study groups without administrative flags
- Broaden Sample to each of the 54 S&Ts

FINAL THOUGHTS

- Sample majority was at or under the age of 25 (n=61)/71%; the Adult Learning Model still beneficial
- Statistically significant relationships were established for all RQs
- Large Effect Size for all but two of the RQs (perception of resilience and application of Emotion Control)
- Future research could increase external validity

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QUESTIONS

THANK
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That's all Folks!

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